

CONTINUOUS FIBER COMPOSITE ISOGRID FOR LAUNCH VEHICLE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the use of continuous graphite fiber composite isogrid for launch vehicle fairings. The general functions of a payload fairing are discussed. Continuous fiber composite isogrid is presented as a new approach to be considered for launch vehicle fairings. Preliminary design equations for composite isogrid are presented. Design loads for various size fairings are discussed and preliminary designs are generated for a variety of fairing constructions. The manufacturing process for composite isogrid is presented. The process was demonstrated on several flat panels and subscale cylinders.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hardware for launch vehicle applications must be lightweight in order to maximize the payload that can be placed in orbit. One of the primary components of a launch vehicle is the payload fairing (Figure 1). The fairing protects the payload from aerodynamic loads and heating during ascent through the atmosphere. Once outside the atmosphere, the fairing separates from the launch vehicle, exposes the payload, and allows it to be placed into orbit. Decreasing the weight of the fairing allows the user to increase the weight of the payload.

At present, most large fairings are constructed from aluminum isogrid. Metallic isogrid consists of a thin skin with integral equilateral triangle stiffening ribs machined onto the surface. This paper studies the weight savings that can be achieved by converting the aluminum isogrid fairing structures into carbon fiber based composite isogrid structures.

A methodology for designing composite isogrid fairing structures has been developed. The methodology is based on preselecting the margins of safety for rib buckling, pocket buckling, and general instability. An automated procedure was used to modify the isogrid geometrical parameters (rib height, width, skin thickness, and triangle height) in the presence of multiple constraints (maximum rib height to width ratio, minimum skin thickness, minimum rib height and width, and minimum triangle height) until the design criteria were satisfied.

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Figure 1. Typical Payload Fairing After Separation

A variety of launch vehicle payload fairings were studied to determine the weight savings achievable with composite isogrid. Alternate composite constructions such as sandwich and monocoque were also studied and their weight savings were compared with composite isogrid. The weight savings achievable with composite isogrid was shown to be a function of the fairing size and the fairing loading.

2. DESIGN LOADS AND DESIGN PARAMETERS

In order to understand the effects of fairing size on the advantages of composite isogrid, multiple fairing sizes were studied. Figure 2 presents the design limit loads for axial load, bending moment and shear force for a 6 foot diameter fairing. Table 1 lists the resulting line loads for the fairing diameters which were used in the design study.

Table 1. Limit Design Loads				
	4 ft.	6 ft.	10 ft.	16 ft.
Peak Line Load $P / 2\pi R + M / \pi R^2$ (lbs/in)	548	808	720	898
Transverse Shear $V / \pi R$ (lbs/in)	176	260	235	155
External Pressure pR (lbs-in)	11	16	0.0	0.0

Figure 2. Six Foot Diameter Fairing Loads

For both the sandwich and isogrid fairings, a set of design assumptions was used. The composite isogrid design parameters are:

- | | | |
|------------------------------------|---------|-----------------------------|
| 1. Minimum skin thickness | = | 0.030 inches |
| 2. Minimum rib spacing | = | 3.5 inches |
| 3. Minimum rib width | = | 0.060 inches |
| 4. Maximum rib height/width | = | 10.0 |
| 5. Factor of Safety | = | 1.25 |
| 6. Minimum Margins of Safety | | |
| Pocket Buckling | = | 0.0 |
| Rib Buckling | = | 0.40 |
| Interbay Buckling | = | 0.20 |
| 7. Material Unidirectional Modulus | | |
| IM7/Epoxy | $E_C =$ | 22.6×10^6 psi |
| AS4/Epoxy | $E_C =$ | 17.0×10^6 psi |
| 8. Skin - layup | | pseudo isotropic, symmetric |
| 9. Rib - layup | | unidirectional |

The design assumptions for the composite sandwich designs are:

1. Minimum Face Sheet Thickness = 0.028 inches
2 plies woven cloth [0/90, ±45]
2. Minimum Core Thickness = 0.250 inches
3. Core Material = Nomex Honeycomb
= 4.3 lbs/cu ft
4. Factor of Safety = 1.25
5. Minimum Margins of Safety
Interbay Buckling = 0.20

3. COMPOSITE ISOGRID DESIGN EQUATIONS

Composite isogrid launch vehicle fairings are buckling critical structures. There are three modes of buckling: pocket buckling, rib buckling and general instability. This section explains how the equations for buckling were modified to consider all the unique properties of the composite isogrid.

Pocket Buckling

$$N_{cr} = \sigma_{cr} t \left(1 + \frac{E_{rib}}{E_{skin}} \frac{bd}{th} \right)$$

where

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{k_L}{12} \frac{11.0 \pi^2 E_{skin}}{(1 - \nu^2)} \left(\frac{t}{h} \right)^2$$

k_L = constant which depends on layup.

Rib Buckling

where

$$N_{cr} = \sigma_{cr} t \left(\frac{E_{skin}}{E_{rib}} + \frac{bd}{th} \right)$$

where

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E_{rib}}{12 (1 - \nu_x \nu_y)} \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^2 + G_{xy} \left(\frac{b}{d} \right)^2$$

General Instability

$$N_{x_{cr}} = 0.605 \gamma E^* t^{*2} / R$$

$$N_{y_{cr}} = 0.936 \gamma^{0.5} E^* t^{*2.5} / R^{0.5} L$$

$$N_{xy_{cr}} = 0.933 \gamma^{0.75} E^* t^{*2.25} / R^{0.75} L^{0.5}$$

t^* and E^* are the thickness and modulus of a plate which has the same extensional and bending stiffness as the composite isogrid. γ is the knockdown factor defined by NASA SP-8007, Buckling of Thin-Walled Circular Cylinders.

4. FAIRING DESIGNS

The design loads in Section 2 were used with the equations given in section 3 to determine the minimum structural weight for each size fairing. Composite isogrid designs were developed using both 33 Msi (AS4 class) fibers and 40 Msi (IM7 class). These designs were compared against traditional aluminum isogrid designs and composite sandwich designs.

Table 2 lists the resulting composite isogrid design dimensions. All shell designs were constrained by the minimum rib spacing of 3.5 inches. Table 3 lists the design dimensions for sandwich construction shells. Each of these designs were constrained by the minimum face sheet thickness of 0.028 inches. A weight comparison between composite isogrid, composite sandwich, and aluminum isogrid is given in Table 4.

Cylinder Dia.	4 ft.		6 ft.		10 ft.		16 ft.	
	AS4	IM7	AS4	IM7	AS4	IM7	AS4	IM7
Skin Thickness	.050	.046	.055	.052	.051	.048	.052	.048
Rib Spacing	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5
Rib Width	.060	.060	.065	.061	.072	.068	.090	.086
Rib Height	.27	.25	.41	.37	.49	.44	.63	.57
Cylinder Length	48	48	72	72	120	120	60	60
Cylinder Weight	27	25	72	67	215	195	222	199

Cylinder Dia.	4 ft.		6 ft.		10 ft.		16 ft.	
	AS4	IM7	AS4	IM7	AS4	IM7	AS4	IM7
Face Sheet Thickness	.028	.028	.028	.028	.028	.028	.028	.028
Core Thickness	.25	.25	.25	.25	.30	.25	.48	.39
Cylinder Length	48	48	72	72	120	120	60	60
Cylinder Weight	36	36	81	81	233	228	211	203

Construction	4 ft.	6 ft.	10 ft.	16 ft.
Al. Isogrid	42	123	372	351
AS4 Isogrid	27	72	215	222
IM7 Isogrid	25	67	195	199
AS4 Sandwich	36	81	233	211
IM7 Sandwich	36	81	228	203
AS4 Monocoque	50	162	533	590

Composite isogrid proved to be the lightest weight design for nearly all four sizes studied. This is a result of the fact that all sandwich designs were limited by the minimum face sheet thickness constraint, which was imposed for handling purposes.

5. FABRICATION AND TESTING

Several composite isogrid flat panels and cylinders that represented typical fairing designs were fabricated using IM-7/977-2. They were tested in axial compression to validate the design methodology described above. Multiple strain gauges were used to measure the strain present in the skin and ribs at failure. Failure load levels agreed well with pretest predictions.

Initially, a series of flat isogrid panels were made. First, a 24.25 inch x 20.75 inch metal isogrid patterned tool with rib thicknesses of 0.053 inch and rib heights of 0.621 inch was fabricated. Silicone rubber was then poured into the tool, and was allowed to cure at room temperature for 24 hours. The rubber mold was removed from the tool and was heat treated with a temperature profile equivalent to the curing process of the advanced composite prepreg. To make the flat panels, the ribs were made by laying up the prepreg tow into the grooves of the rubber mold. The pseudo-isotropic skin was laminated and then placed on top of the ribs. The assembly was then vacuum bagged and co-cured in an autoclave. One panel had a six ply skin with a layup sequence of $(\pm 60,0)_S$. A total of 24 panels were made with a 12-ply skin using a layup sequence of $(\pm 60,0)_{2S}$.

Six isogrid panels were tested under compressive loads. The flat isogrid panels were first machined to 21.5 inch x 14.5 inch and then were placed in a test fixture which constrained the panels only along the two loaded edges. Four of the composite isogrid panels with 12-ply skins were tested to the first load drop, which occurred at an average load of 8304 lbs with a variance of 3 percent. One 12-ply skin panel contained a layer of viscoelastic vibrational damping material between the sixth and seventh plies, and it reached a load of 7900 lbs. This indicated that the incorporation of one ply of damping material had little effect on the overall compressive strength of the composite structure. The one panel with a 6-ply skin gave a maximum load of 3560 lbs to the first load drop.

For isogrid to be a cost-effective alternative for fairing construction, automated fabrication techniques are necessary. A 2-foot diameter composite isogrid cylinder was fabricated using filament winding for the ribs and skin. The filament winding mandrel was made by attaching several flat sections of the rubber isogrid mold to a cylindrical mandrel. The manufacturing process produced a high quality part in significantly less time than the hand layup process.

A recent development has been the use of composite isogrid for spacecraft solar panels. The preliminary design study determined that the composite isogrid had a slight weight savings compared to composite sandwich panels. For a particular spacecraft, the detail design of a composite isogrid solar panel was completed and a number of panels fabricated. Figure 3 shows a photo of a completed 4-foot x 2-foot panel. Development work is continuing to reduce the thermal distortion which occurred during curing at 350°F.

Figure 3. Composite Isogrid Solar Panel